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Research Article

Development Of a Novel by RP – HPLC Method for The Estimation of Glatiramer Acetate

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, an attempt was made to provide newer, sensitive, simple, accurate and low cost HPLC methods. It is successfully applied for the determination of Glatiramer acetate in pharmaceutical preparations without the interferences of other constituents in the formulations new RP-HPLC method was developed for both bulk drug and formulation. These proposed methods give reliable assay results with short analysis time (<10.0 min) using the mobile phase of (Acetonitrile: Trifluoroacetic acid) with 1.0 ml/min flow rate is quite robust. The optimum wavelength for detection was 220 nm at which better detector response for drugs was obtained. The wavelength was found to be 220nm for Glatiramer acetate. The average retention time for Glatiramer acetate was found to be 9.039min respectively. System suitability tests are an integral part of chromatographic method. They are used to verify the reproducibility of the chromatographic system. To ascertain its effectiveness, system suitability tests were carried out on freshly prepared stock solutions. The HPLC calibration was linear in concentration range of 80-120% with regression 1.000 for Glatiramer acetate. The low values of % R.S.D. indicate that method is precise and accurate. The mean recoveries were found in the range of 99.74-100.02 % for HPLC. These results show the accuracy and reproducibility of the assay. Ruggedness of the proposed methods was determined by analysis of aliquots from homogeneous slot by different analysts, using similar operational and environmental conditions; the % R.S.D. reported was found to be less than 2 %. The proposed method was validated and the results of all methods were very close to each other as well as to the label value of commercial pharmaceutical formulation.

INTRODUCTION

High Pressure Liquid Chromatography

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High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is a process of separating components in a liquid mixture. A liquid sample is injected into a stream of solvent (mobile phase) flowing through a column packed with a separation medium (stationary phase). Sample components separate from one another by a process of differential migration as they flow through the column.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Preparation of mobile phases

Mobile phase A: Mix 1ml of trifluoroacetic acid in 1000ml of purified water, filter through 0.45 μ m membrane filter and degas.

Mobile phase B: Mix 1ml of trifluoroacetic acid and 1000ml of acetonitrile, filter through 0.45 μ m membrane filter and degas.

Preparation of Glatiramer acetate standard stock solution: Accurately weigh and transfer about 104 mg of Glatiramer acetate into 100ml volumetric flask add 50ml purified water sonicate to dissolve and dilute to volume with purified water.

Preparation of sample stock solution: Accurately weigh 5ml of sample into 100ml volumetric flask shake it well dissolve and dilute to volume with purified water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Fig.1: Optimized Chromatogram

Validation Parameters:

System suitability: The standard Stock solution of Glatiramer acetate was injected six times into HPLC system as per test procedure. The system

suitability parameters were evaluated from standard Chromatograms obtained, by calculating the % RSD of retention times, tailing factor, theoretical plates and peak areas from six replicate injections.

Fig: 2 Chromatogram of Standard solution

Specificity: Solutions of Standard and Sample were prepared as per test procedure and injected into the HPLC system.

Fig: 3. Chromatogram of specificity sample solution

Precision

Repeatability/ Method precision: Six sample solutions were prepared and injected into the HPLC system as per test procedure.

Fig: 4. Chromatogram of Precision sample solution

S. No	Peak Name	RT	Area	%Area
1	Glatiramer Acetate	9.017	29161039	100.00
2	Glatiramer Acetate	9.045	29267819	100.00
3	Glatiramer Acetate	9.029	29269385	100.00
4	Glatiramer Acetate	9.005	29162172	100.00
5	Glatiramer Acetate	9.027	29240159	100.00
6	Glatiramer Acetate	9.011	29215121	100.00
Mean		9.02	29219283	
Std.Dev		0.01	48935	
%RSD		0.16	0.17	

Linearity: 100 mg of glatiramer acetate was dissolved in 20ml of diluent (water). The concentration of the solution was 5000 μ g/ml from this parent solution, 10 ml was diluted to 100ml to get a concentration of 500 μ g/ml from this solution, solutions of various concentrations such

as 80,90,100,110,120 μ g/ml of glatiramer acetate were prepared using water (purified water) as diluent. 50 μ l of each of the solutions was injected into the HPLC system and the run time was 30 minutes for each injection.

Fig: 5. Chromatogram of Linearity sample solution

Linearity/Calibration Graph of Glatiramer Acetate

Figure: 6 Graph for Linearity Data

Accuracy: Assay was performed in triplicate for various concentrations of Glatiramer acetate equivalent to 80, 100 and 120 % of the standard amount was injected into the HPLC system as per the test procedure.

Fig: 7. Chromatogram of Accuracy sample solution

Accuracy data

Sample No.	Spike Level	Amount (mg) added	Amount (mg) found	% Recovery	% Mean Recovery	SD	%RSD
1	80 %	0.81	0.809	100.11	100.02	0.16	0.160

	80 %	0.81	0.808	100.03			
	80 %	0.81	0.807	99.91			
2	100 %	1.01	1.007	99.78	99.74	0.17	0.170
	100 %	1.01	1.007	99.71			
	100 %	1.01	1.007	99.73			
3	150 %	1.21	1.209	99.76	99.77	0.17	0.170
	150 %	1.21	1.209	99.76			
	150 %	1.21	1.209	99.80			

Robustness: The robustness of the proposed method was determined by analysis of aliquots from homogenous lots by differing physical parameters like flow rate, organic content, wavelength and mobile phase composition which

may differ but the responses were still within the specified limits of the assay.

Standard Chromatogram for Robustness (Temperature)

Sample Chromatogram for Robustness (Temperature)

CONCLUSION:

All the above methods do not suffer from any interference due to common excipients. Therefore, it was shown that the proposed methods could be successfully applied to estimate Glatiramer acetate. Thus, the above studies and findings will enable the quantification of the drug for future investigation in the field of analytical chemistry.

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